

TWO q -IDENTITIES FROM THE THEORY OF FOUNTAINS AND HISTOGRAMS PROVED WITH A TRI-DIAGONAL DETERMINANT

Helmut Prodinger¹

*The John Knopfmacher Centre for Applicable Analysis and Number Theory, School of Mathematics,
University of the Witwatersrand, P. O. Wits, 2050 Johannesburg, South Africa*

helmut@maths.wits.ac.za

Received: 8/27/04, Accepted: 2/3/05, Published: 2/8/05

Abstract

Two identities required in the theory of fountains and histograms are easily proved by expanding a tri-diagonal determinant (reminiscent of Schur's) in two different ways.

We consider the following infinite tri-diagonal determinant (elements not displayed are zero)

$$\text{Schur}(x) := \begin{vmatrix} 1 & \overbrace{0 \dots 0}^{p-2} & & xq^1 & & & \dots \\ -1 & 1 & & 0 \dots 0 & & xq^2 & \dots \\ & -1 & 1 & & 0 \dots 0 & & xq^3 & \dots \\ & & -1 & 1 & & 0 \dots 0 & xq^4 & \dots \\ & & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \ddots \end{vmatrix}.$$

Schur, when providing his proof of the Rogers–Ramanujan identities in 1917 [3] used a similar determinant; since I am advocating that Schur's work deserves to be better known, I use the name $\text{Schur}(x)$. This short note shows that two identities that were required in the study of fountains and histograms [1] are most easily proved by expanding the determinant in two different ways.

Expanding the determinant with respect to the first column (“top–recursion”) we get

$$\text{Schur}(x) = \text{Schur}(xq) + (-1)^p xq \text{Schur}(xq^p).$$

¹Dedicated to Kathy Driver for six years of loyal support.

Thanks are due to a friendly referee who pointed out some trouble with signs.

Setting

$$\text{Schur}(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n x^n,$$

we get, upon comparing coefficients,

$$a_n = q^n a_n + (-1)^p q^{1+p(n-1)} a_{n-1} = \frac{(-1)^p q^{1+p(n-1)}}{1 - q^n}.$$

Since $a_0 = 1$, iteration leads to

$$a_n = \frac{q^{n+p} \binom{n}{2} (-1)^{pn}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2) \dots (1 - q^n)}.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Schur}((-q)^{p-1}) &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{(-1)^n q^{n+p} \binom{n}{2}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2) \dots (1 - q^n)} q^{(p-1)n} \\ &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{(-1)^n q^p \binom{n+1}{2}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2) \dots (1 - q^n)}. \end{aligned}$$

Now consider the *finite* determinants $\text{Schur}_n(x)$, obtained from $\text{Schur}(x)$ by taking the first n rows and columns. Expanding this determinant with respect to the last row (“bottom–recursion”) we get

$$\text{Schur}_n(x) = \text{Schur}_{n-1}(x) + (-1)^p x q^{n-p+1} \text{Schur}_{n-p}(x).$$

In particular,

$$\text{Schur}_n((-q)^{p-1}) = \text{Schur}_{n-1}((-q)^{p-1}) - q^n \text{Schur}_{n-p}((-q)^{p-1}),$$

and $\text{Schur}_j((-q)^{p-1}) = 1$ for $j = 0, \dots, p - 1$. The quantities $\text{Schur}_n((-q)^{p-1})$ were called E_n in [1] (with matching initial conditions $E_j = 1$ for $j = 0, \dots, p - 1$). Whence we proved

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} E_m = \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{(-1)^n q^p \binom{n+1}{2}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2) \dots (1 - q^n)}.$$

Merlini and Sprugnoli had asked for a direct proof, which was given in [2], by showing an explicit form for E_m . The present proof avoids this and is thus simpler.

A second (similar) formula was also requested, namely

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} D_m = \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{(-1)^n q^{n+p} \binom{n}{2}}{(1 - q)(1 - q^2) \dots (1 - q^n)}.$$

for $D_n = D_{n-1} - q^n D_{n-p}$ and (different) initial values $D_j = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^j q^i$ for $j = 0, \dots, p - 1$. This follows immediately by setting $D_n = \text{Schur}_{n+p-1}((-1)^{p-1})$.

References

- [1] D. Merlini and R. Sprugnoli, *Fountains and histograms*, J. Algorithms **44** (2002), no. 1, 159–176.
- [2] P. Paule and H. Prodinger, *Fountains, histograms, and q -identities*, Discrete Mathematics and Theoretical Computer Science **6** (2003), 101–106.
- [3] I. Schur. Ein Beitrag zur additiven Zahlentheorie und zur Theorie der Kettenbrüche. *S.-B. Preuss. Akad. Wiss. Phys.-Math. Kl.*, 1917, 302–321, reprinted in I. Schur, *Gesammelte Abhandlungen*, vol. 2, pp. 117–136, Springer, 1973.